

FRACTIONAL RECOVERY OF APPLIED PHOSPHORUS IN SOILS OF KOGI STATE, NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Ten composite surface soil samples representing the distinct geological formation of Kogi state north central Nigeria were treated with various concentration levels of phosphorus and the amount of phosphorus measured at intervals of 1, 28 and 42 days. The phosphorus fixing capacities of the soils increased with increasing levels of P addition and equilibration time. At 1 day, phosphorus fixation capacities estimated by fractional recovery ranged from 2 to 49% and at 42 days observation it varied from 27 to 63%, respectively. The amount of phosphorus required to raised the value of Bray P-1 by 1mgL^{-1} (Fertilizer factor) at 42 days varied from 1.25 to $5/25\text{mgL}^{-1}$ with a corresponding mean of 2.371mgL^{-1} . The fertilizer fraction seemed to provide a useful guideline of obtaining the phosphorus fertilizer needs of the soil.

KEYWORDS: Fractional recovery, phosphorus fixation capacities, fertilizer factor, and Bray P-1

INTRODUCTION

Researches on the ability of the soils to retain and release phosphorus have been widely studied (Okeya, 1977; Ayodele and Agboola 1981). It had been noticed that a lot of factors have been responsible for P adsorption and desorption reaction in soils, such as soil type, amount of P applied in the soil, reaction and microbiological (Ayodele and Agboola 1981) activities among others. Okeya (1977) explored the possibility of making fertilizer recommendation based on sorption or fixation studies. He used the term fractional recovery which is defined as the proportion of added nutrients (P) to the soil that is extracted by an extractant after a given period of time. He also found out that fractional recovery decreased with time.

Fractional recovery involved the applied P measurement in the soil by means of soil test method used in estimating available P form. The added P fraction not recovered is taken as the P fixed or adsorbed by the soil when known rates of P are applied to the soil and allowed to equilibrate for sometime after which Bray P-1 extractant values are determined at different interval.

Tabi *et al* (2007) while working on soils of the Northern Nigeria Guinea Savanna, Nigeria reported a P fractional recovery that ranged from 0.10 to 0.66 with a mean of 0.24. Based on P fertilizer factor, they obtained a potential P supplied of 2 to $1\frac{1}{2}\text{Kg/ha}$ with a mean of 5Kg/ha . Phosphorus fixations by soils control its availability to plant in various degrees (Parfitt, 1979 and Agbenin, 2003).

Wanik (1984) carried out fixation study on P on Ndop soils in the Republic of Cameroon and calculated a fertilizer factor for P to be 4.70, also Osemwota *et al.*, (2000) carried out P sorption studies on soils of Edo State to work out P fertilizer required for the soil test value or P status and obtained P fertilizer that varied from 1.28 to 2.50 with a mean of 1.76.

The used of fertilizer factor has become a familiar procedure in fertilizer recommendation (Ayodele and Agboola, 1981). Fractional recovery helps to established phosphorus fertilizer factor from which P fertilizer recommendation could be based. Ibia *et al.*, (2009) asserted that fertilizer factor produces a useful guide for estimating the P requirements of soils. The authors also reported fertilizer factor of 4.0, 4.4, 5.3, 3.2 and 3.6 for soils formed on river alluvium, coastal plain sands, Beach sand, sandstone and shale, respectively upon the application of 240mg L^{-1} of P.

The objective of this study was to evaluate the P retention ability of soil guinea savanna of Kogi state, North Central Nigeria, with a view to establishing a general basis for phosphorus fertilizer recommendation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ten surface soil samples were used for the study to represent the two (2) distinct geological formations in Kogi state Basement complex and Cretaceous sediments respectively. Two (2) milliliter aliquots of graded concentration of P (0, 200, 400 and 600mgL⁻¹) in 2mls of the diluted CaHP0₄ were equilibrated with 5g of soil in duplicate cups and allowed to stand for 1, 28 and 42 days, respectively. The soils were then kept. This process was repeated for each of the four treatments. 2ml of distiller water was added to the 0 (control) treatment. The extraction bottles were covered in order for the samples to remain moist. The treated samples were incubated for 1, 28 and 42 days, respectively. After the incubation periods, extraction of available P from the moist soil samples was done by Bray P1 method (Bray and Kurtz, 1945). A measure of the fractional recovery (FR) of P by the soils was obtained from the relationship between phosphorus added and the amounts extracted by Bray P-1 method expressed as

$$y = a + bx$$

y = Phosphorus extracted from each soil at a given rate of addition and time of incubation.

x = The rate of P added (mgL⁻¹).

a = Incept of regression line corresponding to extracted P at zero P addition.

The slope (b) of the regression line represents fractional recovery which is the properties of added P recovered at a particular period of time of incubation. From the fractional recovery estimate, the amount of P adsorbed were obtained as the different between P added and P extracted by Bray P1, while, the phosphorus fixing capacity (PFC) was obtained from the relationship.

$$PFC = (1 - FR) 100.$$

Where:

FR = Fractional Recovery at a given time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amount of P recovered as a fraction of time is presented in Table 1 and the relationship is described by regression data in Table 2. Amount of P extracted at each time interval increased with increasing levels of P addition, 0mg⁻¹ addition being the lowest and 600mgL⁻¹ addition being the highest for all the soil groups, a reflection of the fact that amount of phosphorus retained increases with increasing rate of addition. This is in line with Ahmed, (2008) of a significant increase in P adsorption as a result of increasing level of added P in some Australian soils. These soil also showed decreasing amount of extracted (recovered) P from 1 – 42 days. The levels of decrease showed no uniform pattern for individual soil. The rate of decrease is the term reflected in each regression equation (Table 2). The phosphorus fixation capacity based on percentage fractional recovery is presented in Table 3. The phosphorus fixation capacities of the different soils on the basis of parent materials are shown in Table 3. For the Cretaceous sediments, 22.8, 37.8 and 45.8% of the added P were fixed for 1, 28 and 42 days incubation period, respectively. For the Basement complex soils, 18.8, 45.4 and 49.4% of the added P were fixed for the 1, 28 and 42 days incubation periods, respectively. This result was in contrast with what was obtained by Ibia *et al.*, (2009) who found phosphorus fixation capacities of 56, 58, 76, 37 and 70% for river alluvium, coastal plain sands, beach sands, sandstones and shale parent materials respectively in Akwa-Ibom soils of Nigeria. Soils from the Basement complex fixed more added P than Soils from the Cretaceous sediments. Based in 42 days incubation period, Basement complex soils fixed 49.4% of added P while Cretaceous sediments fixed 45.8%.

Generally, these data indicate that the soils have low to medium capacities to absorbed or fix P. Ibia and Udo (1993), obtained wider range of P adsorption capacities in the soil of Southern Nigeria when they used single point adsorption index method of Bache and William (1971).

The use of fertilizer factor had becomes a familiar procedure in fertilizer recommendation (Ayodele and Agboola 1981) fertilizer factor is defined as the amount of an element which is required to increase the soil test value of an

element by 1ppm (1kg/ml). The calculated Ft values for the soils are presented in Table 4. At 42 days of incubation, the mean values ranged from 1.43 to 6.02 with an overall mean for all the soils calculated to be 2.41mgL⁻¹. The value is within the range of 1.28 to 2.50 obtained by Osemwota *et. al.*, 2000 for soils of Edo State of central Southern Nigeria soils. This fertilizer factor has been found useful in making P fertilizer recommendation when soil P test values and critical level of P have been established (Ayodele and Agboola, 1981). This usefulness need to be explored in a wide range of soils using correlation and calibration studies.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that P fixing capacities of three soils increase with increasing rate of P fertilizer addition over time of incubation. At 42 day of incubating the soil samples with graded rate of P, the ability of the soil to fix and retain P varies. On fractional recovery, the fertilizer factor (Ff) calculated from this would seem to provide a useful guide for estimating the P fertilizer requirement of soils. This call for detailed studies to calibrate the P fertilizer factor and correlate field responses of crops to P fertilizer application on a wider range of soils based on fertilizer factor.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, M. F. Kennedy, A.T. Choudnury, M. L. Kecskes, M. L. and Deaker, R. (2008). Phosphorus adsorption in some Australian soils and influence of bacteria on the desorption of P. *Commun. Soil Plant Anal*, 39 (9, 10): 1269-1294.
- Ayodele, O.J. and Agboola, A.A.(1981). The relationship between Bray P-1, modified NaHNO₃, New Mehlich and NH₄F, HF extractants for phosphorus in savannah soils of Western Nigeria. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 45:462-464.
- Bache, B.W. and Williams, (1971). A phosphorus sorption index for soils. *J. Soil Sci.*, 22:289-301.
- Parfitt, R. L. (1979). The availability of P from phosphate goethite bridging complexes. Desorption and uptake by ryegrass. *Plant Soil*, 53:55-65.
- Agbenin, J.O. (2003). Extractable iron and aluminium effects on phosphorus sorption in a savannah Alfisols, *Soil Sci Soc of Am. J.* 67:589-595.
- Bray, R.H. and Kurtz, L.T.(1945). Determination of total , organic and available forms of phosphorus in soils. *Soil Sci.* 59:39-45.
- Ibia, T.O.; Udo, E.J. and Omueti, J.A.I.(2009). Fractional recovery of applied phosphorus in soils of Akwa Ibom State, Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. *Environmental Research Journal* , 3 (1):1-3.
- Okeya, O.O (1977). *Phosphorus fertilizer needs of some Nigeria soils as determined by chemical and green house methods*. M.Phil. Thesis, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Osemwota, I.O.; Ogboghodo, A.I.; Okpefa, G.O. and Njukwe, K.E. (2000). Characterization of soils of Edo State of Nigeria for computation of phosphorus fertilizer factor. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 34(2): 78-84.
- Wanik, S.B.C (1984), *Soil Fertility evaluation for rice (Oryza sativa L) production in Ndop plain of the republic for Cameroon*. Ph.D. Thesis, Department of Agronomy, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

Table 1: Fractional Recoveries (Fr) for different rates of added P (mg/kg) at different lengths of period of incubation

Soil Number	Location	Length of incubation period (days)		
		1	28	42
1	Anyigba	0.981	0.391	0.369
2	Abejukolo	0.767	0.695	0.681
4	Ikanekpo	0.855	0.819	0.673
5	Umoimi	0.735	0.698	0.668
7	Idah	0.512	0.507	0.463
12	Obehira	0.825	0.715	0.730
13	Ihima	0.836	0.392	0.420
14	Ishanlu	0.697	0.188	0.170
15	Ayeterogbede	0.824	0.466	0.464
18	Ofere	0.849	0.625	0.455
Mean		0.781	0.551	0.509

Table 2: Linear regression equation for the relationship between available phosphorus and rates of phosphorus addition with time

	Days	(Y = a+bx)
1) Anyigba	1	Y = 19.40 + 0.824 X
	28	Y = 16.20 + 0.725 X
	42	Y = 22.50 + 0.730 X
2) Abejukolo	1	Y = 6.70 + 0.836X
	28	Y = 45.60 + 0.392X
	42	Y = 20.20 + 0.420X
4) Ikanekpo	1	Y = 32.00 + 0.697X
	28	Y = 4.68 + 0.188 X
	42	Y = 0.90 + 0.176 X
5) Umoimi	1	Y = 14.30 + 0.849 X
	28	Y = 1.80 + 0.628 X
	42	Y = 3.70 + 0.455 X
7) Idah	1	Y = 5.20 + 0.824 X
	28	Y = 27.40 + 0.466X
	42	Y = 15.10 + 0.464 X
12) Obehira	1	Y = 17.20 + 0.981X
	28	Y = 10.70 + 0.391X
	42	Y = 0.88 + 0.367 X
13) Ihima	1	Y = 38.70 + 0.767 X
	28	Y = 2.80 + 0.695 X
	42	Y = 2.40 + 0.681 X
14) Ishanlu	1	Y = 12.30 + 0.855X
	28	Y = 19.20 + 0.819X
	42	Y = 4.30 + 0.673 X
15) Ayeterogbede	1	Y = 48.50 + 0.512X
	28	Y = 8.90 + 0.509X
	42	Y = 13.20 + 0.463X
18) Ofere	1	Y = 17.60 + 0.735 X
	28	Y = 11.91 + 0.698 X
	42	Y = 12.51 + 0.668 X

Table 3 Phosphorus Fixation Capacity Based on Fractional Recovery at different time period

Parent material		Cretaceous Sediments		
S/N	Location	1(%)	28(%)	42(%)
1	Anyigba	2	61	63
2	Abejekolo	23	30	32
4	Ikanekpo	14	18	37
5	Utoimi	26	30	33
7	Idah	49	50	64
	Mean	22.8	37.8	45.8
	Parent material	Basement	Complex soils	
		1	28	42
12	Obehira	17	28	27
13	Ihima	26	61	58
15	Ishanlu	18	53	54
15	Ofere	18	53	54
18	Ayatorogbede	15	32	54
	Mean	18.8	45.4	49.4

Table 4: Data on fertilizer factor calculated from fractional recovery at 42 days of incubation

Soil No	Rate of P addition (mg/kg)		
	200	400	600
1	2.85	2.83	2.72
2	1.89	1.42	1.83
4	2.32	1.52	1.52
5	1.40	1.42	1.47
7	1.66	2.26	2.03
12	1.44	1.25	2.87
13	1.47	2.49	2.21
14	4.75	8.07	5.25
18	2.15	2.44	2.37

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